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Renewing Mechanical and Mechatronics Programs using Studios

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ABSTRACT

In a world of rapid change, engineering programs need to adapt to be relevant. This paper addresses the renewal processes for mechanical and mechatronics engineering programs at a large university of technology. The paper sits within a wider curriculum change movement, including all engineering and IT programs at this university.

Several meetings have been held over the last 3 years with both industry panels and with academic staff and students to understand the nature of the problem. Using a design-thinking approach, we have explored: global trends, the nature of engineering work and projects, the capabilities required by engineers, and the kinds of capabilities that graduates need to operate confidently in this new world of work.

There is a clear need for graduates to be more operational as they move from study to work. Consequently, a major focus on experiential learning is emerging as the key delivery vehicle for new kinds of graduates including projects, studios, and internships. These forms of learning are supported by ready access to online materials as required. A central thread is personalisation of the student learning experience through learning contracts and portfolios.

There has been constant demand for change in engineering education for at least the last 20 years. Making change happen, however, is another matter. We are in the fortunate position at this university to have high level support from the Chancellery and the Dean to move our engineering programs to be more relevant to the future. This paper describes the process for engaging our academics, students and industry supporters in that process and will be of interest to many who are grappling with similar transitions.

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1 OVERVIEW

The 2019 SEFI conference organising committee has identified complexity and emerging technologies as key themes for this year's conference:

Turbulence, interdependency and complexity characterize the operating environment ... Freedom, openness and creativity determine the digital economy. ... New generation of learning technologies and networks are ubiquitous and mobile which reshape access to and delivery of learning.

This paper discusses the on-going work to prepare new programs in mechanical and mechatronics engineering at the University of Technology Sydney (UTS), taking into account complex problems on the one hand and emerging educational technologies and pedagogies on the other.

The paper serves as a roadmap for similar transformations elsewhere. In many ways, curriculum design is not the major issue. Curriculum *change* is the major issue, first for our academic staff who are used to teaching in a particular way, and second for our students, who are often comfortable with an exam-driven system that does not serve them well in the long-term. Learning the standard solutions of the past does not prepare a graduate to invent new solutions for a changing, complex future.

The paper is of obvious interest to those in related disciplines, as they make their own curriculum revisions for a world with rapidly changing industry needs. However, the paper should be of interest to those in other disciplines (not just engineering) because it signposts the *processes* we have used to explore future graduate capabilities from industry, with input from both students and academics, in the nature of the future curriculum.

A studio-based curriculum is proposed, with many examples of suitable studio projects generated by industry, academics and students, which should be of wider interest and inspiration.

2 INTRODUCTION

The 21st century is a time of great change, with job automation and offshoring now overtaking the professions, including engineering and information technology [1]. The professional jobs that are remaining are those that require creative responses to complex problems, and/or with high human contact [2]. Therefore, as university educators, we need to prepare graduates for this new world, including the ability for graduates to start and build their own organisations.

We believe that, to achieve this, learning needs to be much more experiential, based on projects and studios as well as internships, global mobility and other experiential extracurricular activities [3-6]. A studio combines project-based learning with student-led learning, enabling each student in the studio to develop themselves according to their own learning/career plan. The evidence of learning for each student will be their *learning portfolio*.

This form of collaborative learning builds competencies, teaches creativity, and how to deal with complexity. As academics, we also need to model these capabilities.

Andreas Schleicher, OECD Director for Education and Skills, reminded us that the modern world no longer rewards people just for what they know but for what they can do with what they know [7].

Researchers can attest to the value of this kind of learning in terms of educational attainment. Angela Duckworth's *grit* (combination of perseverance and passion) and Carol Dweck's *growth mindset* show causal links to improved performance [8-10].

Further, many reviews of engineering education in the last 15-20 years have urged transformation of engineering education [2, 11-17].

These international reviews recommended several issues to be addressed such as: the ability to deal with complex problems, interdisciplinarity, creativity and invention, leadership, sustainability, global ethics, and lifelong learning [18]. Curriculum changes suggested included: a professional spine, teaching for connection between topics, approximate engineering practice, use case studies, situate problems in the world. The Henley Report [17] recommended three different kinds of engineers: the technical specialist, the integrator and the change agent.

How might we achieve these recommendations, given the evidence of change over the last 15-20 years is scant? Our solution is a curriculum built around studios, borrowing from the design disciplines [19].

3 ABOUT STUDIOS

Capabilities developed in studio learning include grit, resilience, growth mindset, curiosity, collaboration, communication, creativity and sensitivity to sustainability and global concerns. Graduates need an agility of mind and transferable skills to meet future skill needs and give back to their communities.

Studio facilitators work beyond the role of imparting knowledge: they are coaches, critics and expert learners. Feedback loops are critical in studios, with students and educators providing regular feedback to one another to achieve quality learning. Education Professor, John Hattie, reminds us that the biggest effects on student learning occur when teachers become learners of their own teaching, and when students become their own teachers [20]. Students in studios have the flexibility to engage in hands-on activities.

The aim of studios is to prepare students for a lifetime of creating new solutions and thriving in a fast-changing world. Traditional subjects are complemented with real-world problems where students can apply their knowledge to collaborative problem-defining and creative problem-solving using and learning both technical rationale and professional capabilities.

3.1 Studios in FEIT

As early as 2014, studios have been used in software engineering to immerse students in real projects with industry partners [21, 22]. These studios were initially extracurricular, with students able to use work they were doing in the studios as replacement assessment tasks in their formal subjects.

From 2015, it was decided to integrate studios into all of the programs in the Faculty, both engineering and IT. The first discipline was Data Engineering, a new program that replaced the former ICT (Information and Communication Technology) Engineering program. This launched in 2017 [6, 23]. Electronic engineering followed in 2018 and electrical engineering in 2019. Mechanical and mechatronics programs will launch in 2020 with civil engineering in 2021.

3.2 Why Studios?

Engineering and Information Technologists use design processes to solve complex problems and to develop new product opportunities [24-26]. The Faculty's *Graduate*

Attributes, adapted from [27], embody the capabilities necessary for professional practice. A graduate is expected to be able to:

- A. Investigate the stakeholder's *needs*,
- B. Use a systematic *design process*,
- C. Apply disciplinary *technical skills*,
- D. *Communicate and coordinate tasks with co-workers*,
- E. *Self-manage tasks, projects and career development*,
- F. While demonstrating *social responsibility*.

Although there has been a history of project-based learning in the Faculty for many years, we are now planning to take this to the next level, shifting the emphasis from Projects to Student Learning. Studios embody that shift [6].

Studios provide students with project opportunities to develop the full range of professional capabilities. Each student defines a set of intended outcomes in a learning contract and then works on satisfying them, which they then document in a personal *e-portfolio*. Studios are graduate attribute E in action – self-management and self-learning for career development.

A challenging task requires first an understanding of its *context*, the system in which it is embedded: the client *needs* must be identified, formally recorded as the *requirements* to be delivered (point A above). These authentic project tasks are intended to be developed with industry partners.

Students use a *design process* (point B), empathising with the stakeholders to understand the problem as deeply as possible [28-30]. Is the problem clear? Are the requirements clear and deliverable?

In the process of developing a set of potential solutions and in evaluating them against the requirements, various kinds of technical (modelling) skills will be required (point C).

Engineering and IT (E&IT) rarely happens as individual activity – *teams* are required almost always. *Communication and coordination* are key skills (point D), likely the most important skills across a career. E&IT professionals spend around 60% of their time communicating both within the team and across team boundaries [31, 32].

Self-management (point E) is a key ingredient. Engineers and IT professionals must be able to manage their work, learning and time to become reliable and productive team members. The studios require students to maintain a reflective journal that will help them to identify strengths and weaknesses, to shape their learning across technical and non-technical capabilities.

Finally, studios will help students to see the global nature of engineering and IT practice, both in the context of problems and design opportunities but also in the nature of the teams in which they will work, blending cultural and disciplinary perspectives.

The studio is the *vehicle* for each individual's learning, as part of their overall career development at the university. Their personal e-portfolio is a record of their achievement of the graduate capabilities and of their readiness to step into the world of work. It will contain many examples that might be discussed at a job interview, demonstrating the graduate is work-ready.

4 THE UNIVERSITY BACKGROUND

This University is committed to produce graduates who [33]:

1. are equipped for **ongoing learning and inquiry** in their personal development and professional practice,

2. operate effectively with the **body of knowledge** that underpins professional practice and
3. are committed to the actions and responsibilities of a **professional and global citizen**.

To formalise these ideas, in late 2014, the University articulated the *Learning.Futures* model of learning comprised of [34]:

1. An integrated exposure to **professional practice** through dynamic and multifaceted modes of practice-oriented education
2. Professional practice situated in a **global workplace**, with international mobility and international and cultural engagement as centre piece
3. Learning that is **research-inspired** and integrated, providing academic rigour with cutting edge technology to equip graduates for life-long learning

Many universities have similar commitments through their learning and teaching strategies.

Learning.Futures, however, has mandated key shifts in *classroom practice*:

1. **Authentic** professional tasks with authentic assessment
2. **Flipped learning** using the best online materials (from here and elsewhere)
3. **Collaborative** learning activities, e.g. inquiry-based activities, labs, studios, projects
4. **Real-life experiences**, e.g. internships, community projects, competitions
5. **Diagnostic feedback** [34]

4.1 The Faculty Context

The Faculty of Engineering and Information Technology has a long history of engagement with practice-based learning [35]. The revised curriculum from 1998 emphasised professional formation, personal development, and academic development. The curriculum became practice-oriented and learner-centred, embodying environmental and social sustainability.

The Faculty of Engineering and IT has interpreted the University Context as:

To create, develop and disseminate world class technological knowledge equipped engineering and IT graduates, to contribute in a global environment, and to co-create value with industry and the community.

Within learning and teaching, our intent is to:

1. consolidate a **flexible, practice-oriented, and inclusive learning environment** that creates graduates who are sought after and globally competitive
2. integrate and encourage **innovation and entrepreneurship** into our courses and research
3. **integrate teaching and research**
4. focus on key areas where we can make a difference to the world through **trans-disciplinary approaches** and the science of engineering

The challenge is to enact this fine rhetoric! The remainder of the paper sets out the process we have used in designing our new programs, specifically, the mechanical and mechatronics engineering programs. As Stephen Covey says: “begin with the end in mind” [36].

5 STEP 1: INDUSTRY CONSULTATION

At the November 2016 Program Advisory Board meeting, we laid the foundation for revising the mechanical and mechatronics engineering programs. Four key questions were addressed, based on some earlier work at the Royal Melbourne Institute of Technology [37]:

1. What are the *global trends* affecting your business/organisation?
2. How are these affecting the *nature of work* and *projects* in your organisation?
3. What does this mean for the kinds of *capabilities* that your people need to be successful?
4. How does this affect the kinds of *graduates* that you want to employ?

There were 18 industry representatives at the meeting, from a range of organisations, covering mechanical and mechatronics engineering as well as electrical and biomedical engineering. Ideas clustered into:

1. Technical (commercially-based, people-based, and manufacturing-based)
2. Non-technical (design tasks versus planning tasks)

There was collective agreement that skills that the university should provide include:

1. 'hard' competencies: Costing; Commercial/legal/regulatory; Designing to specification; Trade skills
2. 'soft' skills: Confidence; Critical thinking; Arguing your case; Persistence; Remote communication; Customer centricity; Teamwork and leadership; Interpersonal skills

A subsequent industry meeting on November 2017 explored project topics for future studios. Some suggestions were:

1. Design and build a sun-tracking solar panel array
2. Design and build a mechanical overspeed brake, aimed at minimising stopping distance
3. Design and fabrication of surface acoustic wave sensor (multidisciplinary)
4. Design and build a reversing linear drive
5. E-bike conversion

6 STEP 2: STUDENT INPUT

A small group of student representatives also provided input during 2017. They saw positives in the old, more traditional approach as one that's familiar, coming from high school. They recognised that the current design and build subjects were helpful (Introduction to Mechanical Engineering and Mechanical Design) with a hands-on approach in some other subjects (e.g., Manufacturing Engineering, Advanced Manufacturing).

They saw negatives in the old curriculum, which they saw as not as hands-on as students are led to believe in the promotion materials for the university. Almost every subject was textbook learning/reading, with some exceptions listed above. They believed that the final exams are stressful and lead to much learning for, and forgetting after the exam. Hands on workshop time is also lacking. Design philosophy is not well implemented in most subjects. The degree as it is, is not a realistic representation of real-world engineering.

They saw the positives of a new project-based, studio-based curriculum as modelling real-world mindset for engineering: learn the fundamentals first and develop advanced skills when necessary for completion of projects, maybe with the assistance of online

modules. Academics should mentor students in the projects as required. This mentorship is what happens in engineering workplaces; why not start at university?

Eliminate exams wherever possible. This frees up focus for professional/personal development of students in engineering capacity and reduces stress and improves mental health. Alternative assessment modes will be required.

Integrate the core subjects of Project Management and Economics and Finance into the progression of projects, i.e. learn what you need as the project goes on, rather than have them as separate subjects.

Overall, students found that a new project-based curriculum would benefit students significantly more than the current system.

7 STEP 3: STAFF (FACULTY) INPUT

In January this year, a staff meeting sought to gather input from as many of the staff (academic, technical, administrative) as possible, using the themes of: Trends, Strengths, Methods, Concerns, and Opportunities. Only Trends and Strengths are reported here for space reasons.

7.1 Trends

The discussion of Trends affecting mechanical and mechatronics engineering quickly opened up the breadth of the challenges and opportunities for these disciplines. The breadth of these challenges, below, highlights the difficulty of designing mechanical and mechatronics programs to enable graduates to move into any of these fields:

Safety (all projects should include design for safety), e.g. biomedical implant design; alcohol level sensors for drivers; low noise machinery; airport silencing.

Robots for people offer many opportunities, including embedded systems; sensors and activation; predicting and monitoring; anomaly detection; people detection to track and identify harmful intentions; manufacturing systems; warehouse automation; aged care; micro/nano machines in health robotics; energy harvesting.

Energy Infrastructure (including Smart and Green) includes autonomous charging; batteries; renewable energy equipment; kinetic and thermal energy recovery; energy harvesting; generating electricity in large scales; optimisation of building management systems; efficient air conditioning systems; solar farm design; design of AC unit based on solar thermal energy; hydro dam/pumped hydro system

Autonomous Vehicles are another exciting new area, including vehicle optimisation; personal transportation; traffic coordination; electric vehicles and electric bikes; autonomous footpath delivery

Data-driven applications include: AI techniques for intelligent fault diagnosis; biomedical mechanical devices, e.g. prostheses and other aids; human factors; non-invasive measurement instrument; data driven, process monitoring and control; additive manufacturing; inspection/quality assurance; efficient and mobile vision systems

IoT includes smart materials; smart monitoring of crops; mass-customised manufacturing (CAD/CAE, measurement, ergonomics); smart home (perception, ethics, networking, programming, cybersecurity).

Environmental Sustainability includes clean water, food and resources; robotic growing and harvesting; low cost water treatment and distribution; 'Fatberg' sewer maintenance; population growth modelling with cost/benefit analysis; triple bottle line

(TBL) analysis; smart materials and structures; autonomous mining; robust reliability of mechanical systems.

7.2 Strengths

Our teaching strengths were seen to be well aligned with the proposed direction for more studio-based programs. It was felt that student interaction is already structured to provide a reason to come to campus/class/lab (maybe not in all classes). There are small group, face-to-face learning activities, supported by blended learning in a friendly environment. This is the essence of Learning.Futures (above). Academics endeavour to provide constructive feedback and offer many teamwork activities in which time management skills, critical thinking, and independent-learning is encouraged.

Graduate employability is at the forefront of curriculum intentions across the University. (This Faculty has an internship program that gives all single degree students 2 x 6-month industry placements during their degree). Industrially relevant projects and hands-on practical, active learning joins theory and practice. Nevertheless, this is not how the students saw the curriculum (above).

Teaching is usually research-inspired, with opportunities to be innovative and entrepreneurial. Many research/industry pathways and projects exist. The robotics group, for instance, has many industry-inspired consulting projects, including a bridge inspection robot.

There is encouragement for design with modelling, simulation and optimisation, including a significant infrastructure investment in additive manufacturing facilities.

Graduate employability is a central focus of our University. Academics want graduates who can work with cutting-edge industry relevant technology, who are resilient and able to evolve with changing technologies. This requires industrially relevant programs.

Practice based experience and industry connections are well established. Further, we want graduating students who can tackle global/current issues for an unknown and uncertain future.

We want to be known for good teaching, using flipped learning, to make innovative and lifelong learning graduates. We want to encourage entrepreneurial thinking and self-motivated and collaborative students.

We want to become emerging leaders in engineering education.

8 SAMPLE CURRICULUM DESIGN

The current mechanical engineering program runs over 10 semesters, including two, 6-month work placements (Figure 1). This figure has been colour-coded to indicate mathematics subjects (pink), thermofluids (green), materials (blue), management (brown), machines (grey), potential design and project subjects (yellow), and electives (white). Subject names are in **bold** and pre-requisites are in *italics*.

This University already has developed several programs using three pairs of studios: fundamentals, applications, and professional stages, initially in the data, electronics, electrical disciplines, as explained earlier [6]. Implementing this model into mechanical engineering yields Figure 2.

Note that the studio sequence has absorbed Fundamentals of Mechanical Engineering, the two Manufacturing subjects and the former Design subjects. There was a strong desire in the team to bring together design methodology with the technical (modelling) capability, as well as manufacturing considerations, including design for manufacture.

Stage 1	Stage 2	Stage 3	Stage 4	Stage 5	Stage 6	Stage 7	Stage 8	Stage 9	Stage 10
33130 Maths Mod 1 Core	33230 Maths Mod 2 33130 Maths Mod 1 Core	48221 Engineering Computations 33130 Maths Mod 1 MAJ	41037 Work Integrated Learning 1 12	48641 Fluid Mech 33230 Maths Mod 2 MAJ	48651 Thermo-dynamics 33230 Maths Mod 2 88037 Phys Mod MAJ	48661 Heat Transfer 48641 Fluid Mechanics MAJ	41047 Work Integrated Learning 2 12	Submajor Elective 6	Submajor Elective 6
88037 Phys Mod Core	80101 Chem & Materials Sci Core	48331 Mech of Solids 48620 Fund Mech Eng OR 48321 Eng Mechanics MAJ		48642 Strength of Eng Materials 48331 Mech of Solids MAJ	48250 Eng Eco & Fin 48230 Eng Comm 48240 Design & Inno Fund MAJ	48260 Eng Proj Man 48240 Design&Inno Fund 48122 EPR1 OR 96 CP MAJ		48270 Entrepreneur & Commercialisation 120cp MAJ	Submajor Elective 6
48230 Eng Comm Core	48510 Intro to Elec Eng MAJ	48621 Manufacturing Eng 48610 Intro to MSM Eng MAJ		48640 Machine Dynamics 48620 Fund of Mech Eng MAJ	48660 Dynamics & Control 48640 Machine Dynamics MAJ	48601 Mech Vb & Measurement 48640 Machine Dynamics 48660 Dynam & Control SPR MAJ		41028 Eng Research Preparation MAJ	Submajor Elective 6
48610 Intro to M&M Eng MAJ	48620 Fund Mech Eng 48610 Intro to MSM Eng 88037 Phys Mod 33130 Maths Mod 1 MAJ	48240 Design & Inno Fundamentals 33130 Maths Mod 1 48230 Eng Comm Core MAJ		48600 Mech Design 1 48331 Mech of Solids 48621 Manufacturing Eng 48240 Design&Inno Fund MAJ	48650 Mech Design 2 48642 Str of Eng Mat MAJ	48663 Adv Manufacturing 48650 Mech Design 2 48621 Manufacturing Eng MAJ		48670 M&M Design 48650 Mech Design 2 MAJ	41030 Eng Capstone 6 MAJ

Figure 1: Current mechanical engineering program

Stage 1	Stage 2	Stage 3	Stage 4	Stage 5	Stage 6	Stage 7	Stage 8	Stage 9	Stage 10
33130 Maths Mod 1 Core	33230 Maths Mod 2 33130 Maths Mod 1 Core	48221 Engineering Computations 33130 Maths Mod 1 MAJ	41037 Work Integrated Learning 1 12	48641 Fluid Mech 33230 Maths Mod 2 MAJ	48651 Thermo-dynamics 33230 Maths Mod 2 88037 Phys Mod MAJ	48661 Heat Transfer 48641 Fluid Mechanics MAJ	41047 Work Integrated Learning 2 12	Submajor Elective 6	Submajor Elective 6
88037 Phys Mod Core	80101 Chem & Materials Sci Core	48331 Mech of Solids 48620 Fund Mech Eng OR 48321 Eng Mechanics MAJ		48642 Strength of Eng Materials 48331 Mech of Solids MAJ	48250 Eng Eco & Fin 48230 Eng Comm 48240 Design & Inno Fund MAJ	48260 Eng Proj Man 48240 Design&Inno Fund 48122 EPR1 OR 96 CP MAJ		48270 Entrepreneur & Commercialisation 120cp MAJ	Submajor Elective 6
48230 Eng Comm Core	48510 Intro to Elec Eng MAJ	48240 Design & Inno Fundamentals 33130 Maths Mod 1 48230 Eng Comm Core MAJ		48640 Machine Dynamics 48620 Fund of Mech Eng MAJ	48660 Dynamics & Control 48640 Machine Dynamics MAJ	48601 Mech Vb & Measurement 48640 Machine Dynamics 48660 Dynam & Control SPR MAJ		41028 Eng Research Preparation MAJ	Submajor Elective 6
48610 Intro to M&M Eng MAJ	48620 Fund Mech Eng 48610 Intro to MSM Eng 88037 Phys Mod 33130 Maths Mod 1 MAJ	48240 Design & Inno Fundamentals 33130 Maths Mod 1 48230 Eng Comm Core MAJ		48600 Mech Design 1 48331 Mech of Solids 48621 Manufacturing Eng 48240 Design&Inno Fund MAJ	48650 Mech Design 2 48642 Str of Eng Mat MAJ	48663 Adv Manufacturing 48650 Mech Design 2 48621 Manufacturing Eng MAJ		48670 M&M Design 48650 Mech Design 2 MAJ	41030 Eng Capstone 6 MAJ

Figure 2: Proposed studio model for mechanical engineering

Figure 2 represents a soft conversion to a studio-led curriculum, one that is likely to be easy to implement with existing staff. Most of the technical subjects have been retained, while a strong, integrating design/studio thread has been established. Note that both Engineering Communication (Eng Comm) and Intro to M&M Eng (Mechanical and Mechatronic Engineering) establish the basic collaboration and design skills required for the subsequent 6 studio subjects, which then lead to the Capstone Project as an individual investigation. Thus, students begin to engineer from the first semester, gradually developing their design and investigation skills through each project/studio, documented in their portfolio.

9 CONCLUSIONS

Curriculum transformation is difficult. We have applied design thinking to the process and engaged our key stakeholders – industry friends, students and staff. Key questions for our industry supporters have included: what are the big trends affecting the discipline? How is the nature of work changing? What capabilities will graduates need in the new workplace?

We have asked our students to identify positives and negatives of our existing programs and teaching methods and also to review some proposed studio/project-driven curricula.

Our academics have also identified trends in the discipline and strengths within the existing academic team and organisation (the School and the Faculty). This process enabled them to see that we are already well-equipped to implement a project-based curriculum. The major challenges will be to provide suitable supervision, feedback and assessment in classes of 150-200. This is the next stage of our development work.

The stakeholder engagement described here is more than just collecting ideas and drafting a new curriculum. In many ways, that's the easy part of the work. The

conversations and workshops have been critical in building consensus and enthusiasm for change. We have also run summer studios in the last two years as experimental opportunities for academics to test the studio concept with small numbers of students (10-25) before they embark on classes of 10 times that number. Lessons from those studios are documented elsewhere [5].

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